

Beneath the Steppe: Archaeological Catalogue of an Elite Xiongnu Burial Site

Tamir Ulaan Khoshuu, Central Mongolia (ca. 100 BC – AD 100)

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Satellite and aerial views of the eastern and western sections of the Tamir necropolis. (a) Satellite image (Google Earth, CNES–Airbus); (b) Aerial photo (N. Bayarkhuu) showing graves under excavation; (c) Topographic detail of Tamir (gray: excavated area). The Tamir River is located at the top of the image.

Presentation and Methodology

The necropolis of Tamir Ulaan Khoshuu is located in the Arkhangai region, in central Mongolia, near the confluence of the Tamir and Orkhon rivers. Spanning nearly 22 hectares on a significant granite outcrop, it overlooks the floodplain of the Tamir River. The site is highly visible from both valleys, making it a prominent and remarkable location. The site's topography reveals a gentle slope toward the south and the Tamir River, divided into two parts by a ravine.

This catalog focuses on the eastern section of the necropolis, compiling data from several explorations, and provides the archaeological foundation for the article “Kinship Networks, Socio-Economic Data, and Funerary Rituals: A Xiongnu Example.” (Antiquity, 2026)

The main investigation was conducted by the Franco-Mongolian missions, directed by E. Crubézy and Ts. Turbat, carried out between 2013 and 2019, with the excavation of 52 graves. Two earlier investigations

Map of present-day Mongolia, showing four archaeological sites, including Tamir. The locations of other excavation sites—Egyn Gol, Noin Ula, and Gol Mod—are indicated. Ulaanbaatar: Mongolia's capital.

Aerial view of the eastern part of the necropolis. Stone circles are marked with white circles, and the grave numbers are indicated within each circle. Graves containing immature or adolescent individuals are outlined with dotted circles. The two Turkic graves are shown in red. Drone footage: © M. Mellet.

had already led to the excavation of 5 tombs by Professor Z. Batsaikhan and his team—students from the Department of Anthropology and Archaeology at the National University of Mongolia—between 2001 and 2003 (Turbat 2003), and again in 2005 in collaboration with an American team composed of D. E. Purcell and K. C. Spurr from Northern Arizona University (Flagstaff), as well as D. C. Waugh from the University of Washington (Purcell and Spurr 2006). We would like to extend our sincere thanks to them for allowing the integration of their data into this publication, enabling the most comprehensive view possible of the eastern sector of the necropolis.

The eastern sector thus provides 57 graves containing 61 individuals. The grave goods indicate two periods of occupation: the first dates to the Xiongnu period, with 54 graves for 57 individuals; the second corresponds to a later reoccupation during the Turkic period (Bayarkhuu 2015), with 3 graves for 4 individuals.

To better define the Xiongnu occupation, 14 radiocarbon dates were obtained, indicating funerary use of the eastern sector between 100 BC and 100 AD.

Number of Order	Laboratory	Sample type	Tomb	R_date	Date Retained
Poz-116271	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	24	2045±30	154 BC - 58 AD
Poz-116277	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	37	2040±30	151 BC - 62 AD
Poz-116275	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	36	2025±30	103 BC - 76 AD
Poz-116278	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	41	2020±30	98 BC - 106 AD
Poz-84436	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	28	2020±30	98 BC - 106 AD
Poz-84433	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	17	1995±30	48 BC - 116 AD
UCIAMS250216	University of California, Irvine	Horse bone	22	2015±15	48 BC - 58 AD
UCIAMS250215	University of California, Irvine	Horse bone	13	2000±20	46 BC - 74 AD
Poz-116274	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	30C	1985±30	44 BC - 117 AD
Poz-84432	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	2	1970±30	41 BC - 124 AD
Poz-116279	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	45	1965±30	41 BC - 126 AD
Poz-116273	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	25	1965±30	41 BC - 126 AD
Poz-116270	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	06A	1965±30	41 BC - 126 AD
Poz-84434	Poznań Radiocarbon Lab	Human bone	18	1905±30	30 AD - 218 AD

Excavation and Recording Methods, Reconstruction and Interpretation

The excavation proceeds in several stages.

The first step involves clearing the surface markers. The stone circle is measured and photographed, to be drawn once all the photos are assembled. Today, the stone circle is recorded using a single vertical photograph taken by a drone.

The second step is to excavate half of the central area of the circle to locate the burial pit. A cross-sectional axis is established to allow for a full longitudinal section and the mapping of the burial architecture. Once located, the burial pit is fully excavated across its internal surface, photographed, and measured.

The third stage involves digging the burial pit in regular levels of 40 to 50 cm in the absence of any remains. Each level is photographed, measured, and its depth recorded. When bones, artifacts, or structures are encountered, a specific level is defined, photographed, and recorded. These items are photographed in detail, and the bones or artifacts are inventoried for further study. In the case of a structure, it is described, measured, photographed, and drawn.

Excavation photographs. (a) Stone circle during excavation; (b) Zenith view of a filled stone circle; (c) Excavation of one of the deepest tombs; (d) Stratigraphy showing modern soil, Xiongnu layer, and substrate.

All this information is recorded on a standardized form for each burial, summarizing the data obtained on the pit, any looting, the tomb's architecture, the individual, and the grave goods. This process allows for an understanding and reconstruction of funerary practices and the most accurate possible reconstructions. All this information is presented in this catalog.

A wealth index is provided for the graves analyzed in the article “Kinship Networks, Socio-Economic Data, and Funerary Rituals: A Xiongnu Example.” It is defined by the presence in the grave of fragments of precious stones (jade, jasper), rare pieces of furniture, like gazelle horns, and artefacts made from valuable materials like gold, bronze, or silver. These are associated with personal adornment (belt buckles in gold, iron, or silver; gold and gemstone earrings; gold leaves; and numerous metal ornaments) or horse tack (saddle decorations, harnesses adorned with gold and silver, damascened pieces). Other items relate to ceremonial display, either personal (such as swords and bells) or funerary (such as iron coffin fittings and quadrifoil motifs). Imported goods—coins, mirrors, seals, and lacquered objects—are also present, as are high-quality items such as cauldrons, lamps, a bronze cup, and carved or worked stone objects. Individuals with no objects that could be considered indicators of wealth are classified as index 3, those with one such item as index 2, and those with between two and six items as index 1. The items used to determine the wealth index are marked with an asterisk in the grave description.

Tomb reconstruction and set of archaeological artefacts from tomb 26. (i) Iron lamp, (ii) Ceramics and reconstructed ceramics, (iii) Bow fragments, (iv) Metal belt buckle, (v) bronze buckle.

Plan of the necropolis showing the biological data of the individuals. Non-adolescent immatures are represented by dotted circles; adolescents by circles outlined in grey; and adults by circles outlined in black. Male individuals are shown as circles filled in blue, females in light red, and individuals of undetermined sex in green. The two Turkic graves are highlighted with red outlines, and graves from earlier excavations are marked with grey circles. The size of each circle corresponds to the diameter of the stone structure observed during excavation.

Anthropological Study Methods: Age and Sex Estimation

Age estimation is based on the following criteria:

- For immature individuals (from fetus to 19 years), age is assessed through skeletal and dental growth and maturation processes. The age of children from postnatal stages to 19 years is given based on maturation stages—first dental, defined by Moorrees *et al.* (1963a, 1963b), revised by Braga *et al.* (2005) and Ubelaker (1984) ; then skeletal, through a metric approach based on diaphyseal lengths (Stloukal and Hanakova 1978; Scheuer and Black 2000); and a morphological approach based on the fusion of secondary ossification centers to their primaries (Birkner 1980).

- The age at death for adults (20 years and older) is estimated from bone maturation and degenerative features. The fusion of the iliac crest and the medial end of the clavicle (Webb and Suchey 1985) allowed for the identification of individuals under 30 years old. One method based on degenerative changes focuses on the morphological alterations of the iliac sacro-pelvic surface, following the criteria defined by Lovejoy *et al.* (1985) and Schmitt (2005). These two approaches help refine the age range and, when combined, can narrow the estimated age. In cases where the sacro-pelvic surface is missing or degraded, dental wear was occasionally used to estimate age, following Lovejoy's criteria (1985).

Sex diagnosis is performed on the pelvic bones using a primary approach, and only on mature bones. It is based on metric criteria using the probabilistic DSP method (Bruzek *et al.* 2017). Sex is considered determined when the result is above 95% certainty. When the result is below this threshold, or measurements cannot be taken or are too few, a secondary method is applied using morphological traits (Bruzek 1991), which offers quick execution and reliability close to 95%.

A genetic study was conducted on a sample of 52 individuals (Keyser *et al.* 2021). The results of the molecular-based sex identification were consistent with available physical anthropological data and permitted the determination of the sex of the 17 individuals for whom morphological indicators of sex were not well defined or absent. Since this study, two samples from the 2005 excavations (T97 and T100) have been analyzed, identifying two female individuals.

Genealogy and spatial distribution of tombs in the necropolis

This genetic study (Keyser *et al.* 2021) also revealed two main lineages, as well as their kinship links extending across six generations.

(a) Genealogy over 5–6 generations; Tombs 22 and 20, not part of a lineage but Y-line related, are shown due to their location. (b) Spatial map showing lineages, couples, and parent–child links (red circles or icon: dated individuals).

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Archaeological dataset of tombs excavated by
the french-mongolian field missions

Tomb 01

GPS : 47.76723, 102.44983

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: Undefined, partially excavated in 2003 by Ts. Turbat and his team.

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented southeast-northwest (140° north), measures approximately 3.40 m long, 1.85 m wide and 3.30 m deep, with an estimated volume of 20.8 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style, with stone blocks at the corners. Interior dimensions: 2.55 m in length, 1.40 m wide, minimum height: 0.50 m

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Exterior dimensions: 2.53 m in length, 1.26 m wide at the west end and 1.05 m at the east end, height: 0.50 m.

Food Offering

Right gazelle leg (hind limb) and horse croup.

Other animal remains

Horse: head and forelimbs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function (grave marker, food offering, food waste, symbolic meaning, or other role): Cattle (shoulder), Caprine (body without head), Gazelle (head).

Individual

The individual is a 40-45-year-old man with right acetabular protrusion and an hyperostotic disease or a chondrocalcinosis. Without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, harness (toggles, buckles), lacquer (fragments), jade disk* (fragments), Antelope horn*
Potteries: ?

Wealth index*: 1

Tomb 02

GPS : 47.76713, 102.44983

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 10.90 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 3.75 m long, 2.675 m wide and 3.40 m deep, with an estimated volume of 34.1 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs in the block-bau style, covered with transverse planks held by stone blocks at the walls and corners. Interior dimensions: 2.90 m long, 1.90 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of logs, with an undetermined joining method. The cover consists of longitudinal planks, either assembled or reinforced with battens on top. Exterior dimensions: 2.70 m long, 0.93 m wide, minimum height: 0.30 m.

Food Offering

Horse: ribs, forelimb (humerus); Cattle: forelimb (humerus).

Other animal remains

Horse: head and hind limbs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Cattle (several bones), Caprine (body without head).

Individuals

A total of three women were identified, none of whom were found in anatomical connection. The minimum number of individuals (MNI) was established based on the cranial elements, dental presence and tooth morphology. The remains include:

- Individual A: a very elderly woman, identified from a skull exhibiting endocranial hyperostosis,
- Individual B: a second elderly woman, identified from a mandible whose condyles are incompatible with the glenoid fossae of the temporal bones of individual A's skull.
- Individual C: a middle-aged woman, identified based on teeth with larger morphology than those of the other individuals.

One have bladder stone and the individual A have an internal frontal hyperostosis.

Associated goods

Chopsticks (5), a hairpin or possibly a pharmaceutical scoop (1), a stone polisher, horse harness (bit, iron decorations); mirror* (fragments); adornment (golden/gilded beads), iron buckle, some bronze fragments.

Xiongnu prestige items: chinese seal*, wooden piece of furniture*

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments, bowl)

Potteries: 5 vessels and a lamp located outside the chamber, in the north-west corner.

Other: iron handle (?)

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

Certain elements suggest the intentional concealment of objects: an iron handle was found between the two lower logs in the northeast corner of the funerary chamber, while a ceramic lamp covering a pot was discovered outside, in the northwest corner.

Dating

Relative dating : Sherds of a ceramic vessel, scattered during looting, match fragments found in the fill of Tomb 11. This indicates that Tomb 02 predates Tomb 11, as the sherds originally from Tomb 02 were brought to the surface during looting and subsequently used in the fill of Tomb 11.

Radiocarbon dating: 45 BC - 85 AD (95.4% probability, Poz-84432)

Tomb 03

GPS : 47.76717, 102.44974

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7,05 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented south-east-northwest (230° north), measures approximately 2.80 m long, 1.60 m wide and 2.70 m deep, with an estimated volume of 12.1 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs, approximately 10 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Exterior dimensions: 2.80 m long, 1.30 m wide ; interior dimensions:

2.27 m long, 0.85 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

The coffin is made of thick planks, with an undetermined joining method, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Exterior dimensions: 2.20 m long, 0.59 m wide ; interior dimensions: : 1.75 m long, 0.51 m wide, minimum height: 0.21 m.

Food offering

Vertebrae and sacrum of beef, beef ribs.

Individual

The individual is a 14-15-year-old adolescent girl. The left elbow and forearm are connected, the rest is without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

45 iron rivets

Xiongnu prestige items: gold leaf* (fragment)

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments – seal, bowl)

Potteries: 4 vessels, fragments (2), and a base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 2

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 04

GPS : 47.76717, 102.44964

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 3.70 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented southeast-northwest (140° north), measures approximately 2.65 m long, 0.75 m wide and 1.10 m deep, with an estimated volume of 2.2 cubic meters

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

Shoulder of lamb, placed on the deceased's legs.

Other animal remains

Horse: head used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 30-40-year-old man, found partially in anatomical connection, with periosteal reactions on the lower limbs, a fracture of the 6th right rib, an old and incomplete fracture of the odontoid process of the axis, which occurred when he was young.

Associated goods

Arrows.

Potteries : only few sherds.

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

No coffin.

Remark

The food offering consists of a lamb aged 9 to 11 months, an animal from the current year: with lambing season occurring in the spring, the burial took place in the winter. If lambing occurred between March and May, the burial would have taken place between December and April. Taking the average, with lambing in April, the burial would have occurred between January and March. This could explain its shallow depth, unless the meat was preserved and deposited frozen!

Tomb 05

GPS : 47.7669, 102.44956

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.50 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented east-west (110° north), measures approximately 2.60 m long, 0.95 m wide and 2.95 m deep, with an estimated volume of 7.3 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

It shows signs of looting.

At a depth of 2.25 m, approximately 0.40 m above the coffin, two longitudinal planks were found along the walls of the pit. These likely represent a cover or a flooring structure, upon which lay two large stone blocks and some ceramic fragments.

Architecture

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The cover consists of longitudinal planks, partially preserved in the western half. Interior dimensions: 1.88 m in length, 0.53 m wide at the east end and 0.48 m at the west end, height: 0.35 m.

Food offering

Bundle of ribs from caprines (sheep/goat)

Other animal remains

Horse: hind limb used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine (shoulder, hind limb).

Individual

The individual is a woman, over 30 years old, found without anatomical connection, presenting hyperostotic disease and possible vertebral metastases.

Associated goods

Birch bark (fragments), adornment (beads)
Potteries: 1 (fragments)

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 06A

GPS : 47.76679, 102.44959

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.50 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented south-east-northwest (140° north), measures approximately 3.15 m long, 1.65 m wide and 2.90 m deep, with an estimated volume of 15.1 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks and a cover of 13 transversal planks, with stone blocks at the corners. Interior dimensions: 2.65 m long, 1 m wide, minimum height: 0.30 m. The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, of which only the northeastern and southern walls remain. Interior dimensions: 2.38 m long, 0.55 m wide.

Food offering

The left hind quarter of a young ram, deposited raw in a pot, and the ribs and a tibia from a caprine in another.

Other animal remains

Horse: hind limb used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine (several bones).

Individual

The poorly preserved individual is a woman, approximately 50 years old, presenting a fracture of the right radius identified as a Pouteau-Colles' fracture. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the right lower limb and the left leg, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Spindle whorl, adornment (red jasper bead*)

Xiongnu prestige item: iron cauldron*

Imported item: lacquerware (bowl?)

Potteries: five vessels and a base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 42BC-85AD à 94,5% (Poz-116270)

Tomb 06B

GPS : 47.76677, 102.44954

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented southeast-north-west (150° north), measures approximately 0.70 m long, 0.28 m wide and 0.50 m deep, with an estimated volume of 0.1 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

None.

Individual

The poorly preserved individual is a 6-9 months year-old girl, in anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Adornment, with a necklace composed of 12 beads made of amber, bone, possibly coral, and possibly glass
Pottery: 1 vessel

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Relative dating: The stratigraphic relationship between the two tombs 06 suggests that tomb 06B is chronologically later than tomb 06A, as it disturbs the original arrangement of the surface stone circle associated with Tomb 06A.

Tomb 07

GPS : 47.76663, 102.45022

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 10 m
Inside the circle, a quadrangular stone structure measures 6 meters in length, 5.5 meters in width, and 0.3 meters in height.

Grave pit

The grave pit measures approximately 2.45 m long, 2.45 m wide and 3.05 m deep, with an estimated volume of 18.3 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

Sheep shoulder.

Individual

The individual is a 40-50-years-old woman, presenting a fracture of the right 9th rib. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the right upper limb (forearm and hand), while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Horse harness (bronze leaf-shaped plates, toggles, buckles, and rings), a pouch made of fabric and silk
 Imported items: silk

Specific Funerary Practices

On the western side, at a distance of about one meter, the posterior half of a horse lay in sternal recumbency, with the hind limbs folded beneath it. The head and forelimbs, recovered from the surface, may have served as grave marker or as food waste.

Dating

The harness fittings date the burial to the 8th-9th centuries (Bayarkhuu 2015, 137).

Tomb 08

GPS : 47.76677, 102.44945

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented south-east-northwest (140° north), measures approximately 3.10 m long, 1.50 m wide and 2.60 m deep, with an estimated volume of 12.1 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks and a cover of transversal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.50 m long, 1.15 m wide, minimum height: 0.50 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, approximately 6 to 10 cm wide, with an undetermined joining method. The longitudinal walls are held at the top by transverse wooden battens. On the west side, the coffin rests on a 4.5 cm square transverse wooden batten. Interior dimensions: 2.00 m in length, 0.60 m wide, minimum height: 0.30 m.

Food offering

The hindquarters of a juvenile lamb were placed in a pot, while a bundle of caprine ribs arranged between the pots.

Other animal remains

Horse: hind limbs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse and Caprine (several bones).

Individual

The individual is a 35-40-years-old man, presenting multiple traumatic injuries. He exhibits fractures of the right 8th and 12th ribs, the left 6th, 7th, and 9th ribs, a Monteggia fracture (defensive injury) of the left ulna, a fracture of the right 5th metacarpal, and a fracture of the first phalanx of the 5th metatarsal. Signs of hyperflexion and epitrochlear lesions are characteristic of archery activity. He also presents a healed spondylolysis of the first three lumbar vertebrae and early-stage infection of the last two thoracic vertebrae, possibly indicative of brucellosis. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated. The upper half of the body was found approximately 50 cm above the funerary chamber.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows; horse harness (bit, bone buckle, and rings); iron buckles at the feet (hobble or footwear?).
Imported items: lacquerware (fragments)
Potteries: 5 vessels and a base

Wealth index* : 3

Tomb 09

GPS : 47.7667, 102.44955

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8.80 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented east-west (90° north), measures approximately 2.65 m long, 0.90 m wide and 3.08 m deep, with an estimated volume of 7.3 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Approximately 0.40 m above the coffin, remains of transverse planks were discovered along the longitudinal walls of the pit.

They likely represent a cover or a flooring structure.

Architecture

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method, covered with transverse planks held by stone blocks on the walls and corners. Interior dimensions: 2.02 m long, 0.60 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

Food offering

The right hind quarter of a ram were placed in a pot, while a bundle of caprine ribs was placed between the vessels.

Individuals

The individual is a 30-40-years-old man, presenting with enthesopathy on the anterior surface of the hyoid bone, as well as an avulsion fracture of the distal end of the right fibula, extending to cause a fracture of the articular surface. The skeleton is completely disarticulated, except for a few elements of the feet.

In the fill of tombs 09 and 10, the remains of a boy aged 2.5-3.5 years were found. In tomb 9, a left maxilla and a sphenoid were discovered.

Associated goods

Bow; knife blade; fragments of a wooden handle (possibly from an iron tool), iron buckles.

Potteries: 3 vessels and a base

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 10

GPS : 47.76665, 102.4495

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8.90 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented east-west (80° north), measures approximately 2.70 m long, 0.80 m wide and 3.20 m deep, with an estimated volume of 6.9 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method, with stone blocks at the corners. Interior dimensions: 1.95 m long, 0.65 m wide, minimum height: 0.30 m.

Food offering

A half ewe carcass was deposited in a pot, while caprine ribs placed on top of and between the pots.

Individuals

The individual is a man, over 60 years old, found in anatomical connection, except the head. He presenting multiple traumatic injuries. He exhibits a fracture of the right scapula and two fractures of the lower limbs: one at the proximal third of the right fibula and the other at the distal third of the left fibula.

In the fill of tombs 09 and 10, the remains of a boy aged 2.5-3.5 years were found. In tomb 10, a mandible was found.

Associated goods

Knife and possibly whetstone, in a sheath, placed along the left femur; worn adornment (belt composed of 6 iron plates and three iron rings located on the back, fastened with an iron buckle).
Imported items: lacquerware (knife sheath)
Potteries: 4 vessels and a base used as a lid

Wealth index*: 3

Remarks

The remains of a child link the two tombs, and the stages of dental maturation suggest it is the same individual. Marmot bones were found in the fill of the grave pit.

Tomb 11

GPS : 47.76692, 102.45005

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.40 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented east-west (110° north), measures approximately 3.30 m long, 1.55 m wide and 3.13 m deep, with an estimated volume of 16 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks and a cover of transverse planks. Interior dimensions: 2.45 m long, 1 m wide, minimum height: 0.50 m.

The coffin is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method, with a cover of longitudinal planks, Interior dimensions: 1.85 m long, 0.45 m wide.

Food offering

Sheep thorax and feet, beef ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse: forelimbs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 11-12-year-old adolescent girl. It is represented only by a few elements (head, vertebrae, distal epiphysis of the right femur), all of which are completely disarticulated.

Associated goods

Spindle whorl, bronze belt elements found in the upper fill of the pit and a mallet and pick found outside the burial chamber.

Potteries: sherds and a pot base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

A mallet and pick was discovered outside the chamber, along the southern wall of the pit, near the southwest corner and a ceramic lamp (base) in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Dating

Relative dating : Sherds of a ceramic vessel match fragments found in the fill of Tomb 02. the sherds originally from Tomb 02 were brought to the surface during looting and subsequently used in the fill of Tomb 11. This indicates that Tomb 02 predates Tomb 11.

Tomb 12

GPS : 47.76641, 102.44933

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 9.20 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented south-east-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 2.90 m long, 0.90 m wide and 2.65 m deep, with an estimated volume of 6.9 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method. Interior dimensions: 2.10 m long, 0.65 m wide, minimum height : 0,20 m.

Food offering

Hind limb of a ewe, bundle of caprine ribs and beef ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse: feet used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (tibia).

Individual

The individual is a 25-35-years-old man. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow, arrows and a hairpin or possibly a pharmaceutical scoop, found outside the coffin, along the southern wall of the pit ; horse harness (buckles, rings); knife and whetstone; grinder ; awl ; belt element (plate?).

Pottery: only sherds.

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 13A

GPS : 47.76691, 102.45019

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented south-east-northwest (340° north), measures approximately 1.70 m long, 1.70 m wide and 1.45 m deep, with an estimated volume of 4.2 cubic meters.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

None.

Individual

The individual is a 35–45 years old man, found in anatomical connection. He presents osteonecrosis of two thoracic vertebral bodies and periosteal reactions on three right ribs, supporting an infectious diagnosis.

Associated goods

None.

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Possibly from the Turkish period.

Relative dating : Sherds of pottery and a fragment of a knife tang were found in the fill of tomb 13A, likely displaced during the looting of tomb 13B.

Tomb 13B

GPS : 47.76691, 102.45019

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 14.60 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 5.20 m long, 2.60 m wide and 5 m deep, with an estimated volume of 67.6 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks and a cover of transverse planks. Interior dimensions: 3.10 m long, 2.05 m wide, minimum height: 0.50 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method, with a cover of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.55 m long, 0.85 m wide, minimum height: 0.35 m.

The coffin is decorated with iron bands and quadrilobed motifs. The lid features regularly interwoven bands, 4 to 5 cm wide, forming diamond patterns. Additional 2 cm-wide bands reinforced the longitudinal and transverse walls with vertical strips spaced 42 cm apart—five bands on the longitudinal sides and a central band on each transverse side. A 2 cm-wide band also appears to reinforce the base

of the walls. Each section defined by the metal bands on the lid and walls of the coffin is adorned with an iron quadrilobed motif. Two types of fabric were observed on the reinforcements and quadrilobed motifs: the first, on the outer side, is rather coarse, while the second, in contact with the wood, is finer and features embroidery. This suggests that the coffin was covered with textiles.

Food Offering

Caprine thorax and loin, and horse ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse head and forelimbs, and cattle head used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual. In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Cattle (humerus, femur), Caprine (several bones)..

Individual

The individual is a 35-40-year-old woman. She is represented only by a few elements (head, vertebrae, some ribs, right forearm, right thumb and index finger and right talus), all of which are completely disarticulated.

Associated goods

Chopsticks (2), knife and lacquered sheath, horse harness (gold rivets and silver decorations), adornment* (amber bead, gold earring and stones), wolf talus and phalanx (adornment or game?)

Xiongnu prestige items: iron cauldron* (foot), rivets covered with gold, silver decorations*, gold earring inlaid with blue and green stones*

Imported items: lacquerware (tray, knife sheath, fragments), mirror* (fragments), coins*, silk

Potteries: 3 vessels, fragments (6), minimum 8 pots

Wealth index* : 1

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 46BC-73AD à 95% (UCIAMS250215)
(Librado *et al.* 2024)

2014-13-46

■ silver
■ iron

5cm

2014-13-40/43

Tomb 14

GPS : 47.76689, 102.45041

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.15 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, oriented west-east (300° north), measures approximately 2.08 m long, 2.08 m wide and 1.16 m deep, with an estimated volume of 5 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

Hind shank of sheep.

Individuals

Two individuals are placed within the lateral recesses: to the south, individual A, a 14-15 year-old adolescent, in anatomical connection, and to the north, individual B, her mother, aged 40-45 years, with only the lower limbs in connection and the rest of the skeleton disarticulated.

Associated goods

Horse harness (iron buckles), on the horses
Imported items: mirror (fragments)
Pottery: 0

Specific Funerary Practices

Two horses occupy the central space separating the individuals; the heads and the right forelimb of the horse located to the north are missing. The horse to the south is a "large adolescent," no older than 3.5 years, while the horse to the north is nearly 4 years old.

Dating

Possibly from the Turkish period (7th-8th centuries), based on the presence of horses.

Tomb 15

GPS : 47.7665, 102.44964

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 15 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 3.40 m long, 2.20 m wide and 4.50 m deep, with an estimated volume of 33.7 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, approximately 10-15 cm, in the blockbau style, with a cover of minimal 7 transversal planks, with stone blocks on the walls. Interior dimensions: 2.90 m long, 1.70 m wide, minimum height: 0.36 m. The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.25 m long, 0.80 m wide, minimum height: 0.36 m.

Food offering

Unidentified.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (vertebra, ribs).

Individual

The individual is a woman, over 50 years old, exhibiting endocranial hyperostosis. She is represented only by a few elements (head, left scapula, clavicles, left humerus, vertebrae, left coxal bone), all of which are completely disarticulated.

Associated goods

Probably mortar, harness fitting (gilded rivet), adornment (white, cream, and turquoise glass beads)

Xiongnu prestige items: rivets covered with gold

Pottery: 1 ceramic lamp, found in a disturbed position

Wealth index* : 3

Remark

The tomb was almost entirely emptied of its contents — the bones of the deceased, ornaments, and offerings. Nothing remains in its original place, except for much of the funerary architecture, including the lid of the coffin that originally contained the body. If the lid was replaced after the contents were removed, this suggests that the looting occurred while the wood was still structurally intact.

Tomb 16

GPS : 47.76718, 102.45034

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.75 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (100° north), measures approximately 3.30 m long, 2 m wide and 3.29 m deep, with an estimated volume of 21.7 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

wide at the west end and 1.20 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.55 m.

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom is made of longitudinal planks and the cover, still partially in place, is made of transverse planks. The coffin rests on at least one wooden batten, square in section (4cm), located on the west side, 26 cm from the transverse wall. Interior dimensions: 1.93 m long, 0.80 m wide at the west end and 0.70 m at the east end.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, slightly trapezoidal, is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Stone blocks are placed in the center and at the corners, likely holding in place the elements of a cover. Interior dimensions: 2.25 m long, 1.55 m

Food offering

Thorax and hind shank of sheep, cattle thorax and fish (vertebra in a pot).

Other animal remains

Horse: head (tooth) used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Cattle and Caprine (several bones).

Individual

The individual is a 35-45-year-old woman, presenting with spondylolysis of the 4th lumbar vertebra and osteophytes on the last two lumbar vertebrae (L4-5). Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Chopsticks (2), spindle whorl, harness fitting (buckle), adornment (gilded beads, pendants of fish vertebrae and deer canine)

Imported items: lacquerware (vessel)

Potteries: 3 vessels and a pot base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index* : 3

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, near the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 17

GPS : 47.76726, 102.45037

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (100° north), measures approximately 3.70 m long, 2.10 m wide and 3.60 m deep, with an estimated volume of 28 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

The coffin, also poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom is made of longitudinal planks. The coffin rests on at least one wooden batten, square in section (4cm), located on the east side. Interior dimensions: 2.55 m long, 0.85 m wide.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is made of wood pieces with an undetermined joining method. Stone blocks are placed at the corners and along the walls, likely holding in place the elements of a cover. Interior dimensions: 2.70 m long, 1.69 m wide, minimum height: 0.55 m.

Food offering

Cattle thorax and caprine ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse: feet used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 40-45-year-old man, presenting with a fracture of the maxilla and the left nasal bone. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs (fibulas) and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, sword*, knife and whetstone, chopsticks (2), mallet, ring, bronze button, rod and iron points in a wooden box, adornment (beads)

Xiongnu prestige items: Cauldron* (fragments), bronze cup*, decorated saddle and harness* (2 bits, iron decorations and rivets in gilded bronze and bone), deer antler

Imported items: Lacquerware (2 bowls)

Potteries: 4 pots and a ceramic lamp

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

A saddle and its harness, along with a transport kit in a wooden box, were found outside the coffin to the east, and a ceramic lamp in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 52 BC – 71 AD (95.4% probability, Poz-84433)

T17

Tomb 18

GPS : 47.76724, 102.45015

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8.70 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3.30 m long, 1.60 m wide and 3 m deep, with an estimated volume of 15.8 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, slightly trapezoidal, is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. It rests on at least one wooden batten, square in section (4cm), located on the west side, 50 cm from the east transverse wall. Stone blocks are placed between the walls of the grave pit and the chamber. Interior dimensions: 2.50 m long, 0.97 m wide at the west end and 0.90 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.20 m.

The splitting of most of the bones and grave goods, along with a wall effect in the center and the vertical positioning of some bones suggests the presence of a coffin. Interior dimensions: 2 m estimated length, 0.55 m wide.

Food offering

Horse croup (sacrum).

Other animal remains

Horse: forelimbs and pelvis used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (vertebrae, ribs), Caprine (femur).

Individual

The individual is a 40-45-year-old man, presenting with a sprain-related lesion on the right fibula. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, horse harness (bit, buckle, and iron fastener), chopstick with a spoon end (or hairpin?), knife (fragment), piece of perforated deer stave/beam and two antlers.

Potteries: 2 vessels, fragments (2) and 2 pot bases

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 25 AD – 175 AD (92.4% probability, Poz-84434)

Remarks

Charcoals and ashes were found along the east wall, near the northeast corner.

One of the bow handle reinforcements was found under the coffin; its position suggests that the bow was broken at the time. The presence of the wooden support elevating the coffin allowed this element to partially slide underneath during looting.

2014-18-21

diam. 15.4 cm

2014-18-3

diam. 13.4 cm

Tomb 19

GPS : 47.76734, 102.45009

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 2.20 m long, 1.40 m wide and 2.87 m deep, with an estimated volume of 8.8 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked logs, approximately 8 cm in width, in the blockbau style, with a cover made of transverse planks. Stone blocks are placed between the walls of the grave pit and the chamber. Interior dimensions: 2.06 m long, 1 m wide, minimum height: 0.45 m.

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. The base is covered with a very thin layer of clay. Interior dimensions: 1.80 m long, 0.55 m wide at the west end and 0.65 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.28 m.

Food offering

An ewe loin in a pot and bundles of caprine ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse: head (mandible) used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 40-45-years-old woman, presenting with a flattened right mandibular condyle, a pronounced mandibular torus, lumbar osteoarthritis with intervertebral osteophytes, and a dislocation of the right hip. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Spindle whorl, iron ladle.

Potteries: 2 vessels and fragments (1).

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 20

GPS : 47.76731, 102.45025

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 6.3 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 3.05 m long, 1.35 m wide and 2.57 m deep, with an estimated volume of 10.6 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked logs in the block-bau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Stone blocks are at the walls and corners. Interior dimensions: 2.25 m long, 0.82 m wide, minimum height: 0.28 m.

The coffin, also poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method and a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.90 m long, 0.50 m wide, minimum height : 0.18 m.

Food offering

Lamb thorax and hind limb of a young ram.

Other animal remains

Horse: foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 14-15-year-old adolescent, presenting with multifocal infectious pathology, including periosteal reactions on the inner surface of the ribs, the sternum (with a foamy appearance), the anterior and posterior surfaces of the left scapula, the distal end of the left humerus, the pelvic bones, the left femur, and the tibiae. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Arrows, sword* (hilt and fragments), iron fittings (saddle decorations), harness (buckles and bone objects), adornment (gold earring), 117 caprine tali (Antelope tali*)

2014-20-14

2014-20-16

2014-20-20

2014-20-17

2014-20-7

2014-20-12f

☐ argent	☐ bronze
☐ or	☐ fer
☐ bois	☐ laque
☐ os / bois de cerf / corne	☐ cuir
☐ fibre / organique autre	☐ tissu
☐ ambre	☐ verre
☐ pierre / minéral autre	

5 cm

Xiongnu prestige items: gold earring*

Potteries: 2 vessels, fragments (2), and a pot base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 21

GPS : 47.76725, 102.44988

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 6 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 2.80 m long, 1.59 m wide and 1.93 m deep, with an estimated volume of 8.60 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, slightly trapezoidal, is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.10 m long, 0.90 m wide at the west end and 1.10 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.43 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, 4 to 5 cm wide, with an undetermined joining method and with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.75 m long, 0.90 m wide at the west end and 1.10 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.20 m.

Food offering

Caprine ribs and feet..

Other animal remains

Horse and cattle feet and pelvis used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual. In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine shoulder and hind shank.

Individual

The individual is a 13-14-year-old adolescent girl. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Knife blade (fragments), iron buckle, adornment (black glass beads, bronze earring?)
 Potteries: 1 vessel, fragments (1) and a pot base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 22

GPS : 47.76736, 102.45025

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 9.2 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3.35 m long, 2.35 m wide and 3.70 m deep, with an estimated volume of 29.10 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, approximately 7 cm in width, in the blockbau style, with a cover of

transverse planks held by stone blocks at the walls and corners. Interior dimensions: 2.45 m long, 1.25 m wide, minimum height: 0.30 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, approximately 7 cm in width, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of two longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.20 m long, 0.60 m wide.

Food offering
Unidentified.

Other animal remains
Horse: head (mandible) and foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (thorax, ribs, limb), Caprine (head).

Individual
The individual is a 30-45-years-old woman. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods
Harness (bit, gilded rivets), birch bark (box?), wooden comb (?), iron object with damascened decoration* and bronze rivets (harness or belt), adornment (glass beads)

Xiongnu prestige item: Belt* (buckle and riveted plates), gold decoration*
Imported item: Lacquerware (oval dish)
Potteries: 3 vessels, fragments (2)

Wealth index* : 1

Dating
Radiocarbon dating: 48BC - 58AD (95% probability, UCIAMS250215) (Librado *et al.* 2024)

Tomb 23

GPS : 47.76741, 102.45015

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 11.25 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3.54 m long, 2.10 m wide and 3.60 m deep, with an estimated volume of 26.80 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked

logs, in the blockbau style, with stone blocks at the corners. Interior dimensions: 2.25 m long, 1.10 m wide, minimum height: 0.20 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Interior dimensions: 2.25 m long, 0.60 m wide.

Food offering

None.

Other animal remains

Horse forelimb and cattle pelvis (sacrum) used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is an old man (?), represented only by a few elements (head, vertebrae, left forearm and hand, some bones of right tarse), all of which are completely disarticulated. He presents with severe osteoarthritis of the cervical vertebrae, the left elbow, and the proximal interphalangeal joints of the left middle and ring fingers.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, horse harness (bit, cheek bar and rings)
 Imported item: Lacquerware (fragments)
 Potteries: 1 vessel, fragments (1) and a ceramic lamp

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Remark

Teeth that could not have belonged to the individual (left lateral incisor and first molar, right second premolar and second molar) were found in the fill of the pit.

Tomb 24

GPS : 47.76664, 102.4499

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 16.50 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (150° north), measures approximately 4 m long, 2.50 m wide and 5.30 m deep, with an estimated volume of 53 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style. Interior dimensions:

2.55 m long, 1.75 m wide, minimum height: 0.55 m.

The coffin, also poorly preserved, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method, with a bottom of three longitudinal planks. It rests two wooden battens. Interior dimensions: 2.40 m long, 0.80 m wide.

Food offering

Unidentified.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (vertebrae, ribs), Cattle (ribs, femur), Caprine (head - mandible).

Individual

The individual is a man, over 60 years old, presenting with an inflammatory process affecting the sacroiliac joints and the bodies of the thoracic and lumbar vertebrae.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows in a lacquered quiver, saddle (fragment), spindle whorl (?), sword* (hilt and fragments), belt* (bronze plate)

Xiongnu prestige items: horse harness* (silver and bronze appliqués, gilded rivets, bone cylinder, small chain and damascened phalerae, buckles and rings, bronze bell), iron lamp*

Imported items: Lacquerware (tray, quiver, fragments), bell

Potteries: 0

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

An iron lamp was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, and the harness pieces were located along the southern wall, suggesting intentional concealment.

Remark

A silver coin was found at a depth of one meter during the excavation of the grave pit. It is a drachm struck by King Kavād of the Sasanian Empire of Iran in the 5th century AD. It may indicate the looting of the tomb, unless it is intrusive and fell into a burrow.

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 165BC – 24AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116271)

Tomb 25

GPS : 47.76706, 102.45041

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 19.90 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately at the bottom, 4.40 meters in length, 2.80 meters in width, and 5.50 meters in depth. A step is visible on the western wall, approximately 1 meter above the base of the pit. Above this step, the pit measures 5 meters in length, with a maximum width of 3.10 meters and a minimum width of 2.66 meters at the central narrowing. The total volume of the pit is therefore 75.8 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with a bottom and a cover made of transverse planks, with on the walls and corners. Interior dimensions: 4 m long, 2.30 m wide, minimum height: 0.70 m.

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. The coffin is decorated with silver quadrilobed motifs on lateral walls and cover. Interior dimensions: 2.55 m long, 0.75 m wide at the west end and 0.88 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.57 m.

Food offering

Half loin of mutton (ewe), horse and cattle ribs and a goose. Gazelle remains found in the fill of the pit.

Other animal remains

Horse heads (mandibles), horse and cattle limbs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (ribs), Cattle (limbs).

Individual

The individual is a 30-35-years-old man. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Arrows, horse harness (bit, appliqués in bone, silve, and bronze, gilded rivet), adornment (bead), chopstick (1).
 Xiongnu prestige items: belt buckle in gold*, decorations in gold*, bronze and turquoise*, Antelope horn*
 Imported: lacquerware (fragments).
 Potteries: 4 vessels.

Wealth index*: 1

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 42BC – 85AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116273)

Tomb 26

GPS : 47.76732, 102.45056

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 13.30 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 3.55 m long, 2.15 m wide and 3.86 m deep, with an estimated volume of 29.5 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style, with stone blocks at the corners. Interior dimensions: 2.60 m long, 1.25 m wide, minimum height: 0.45 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.40 m long, 0.50 m wide, minimum height: 0.31 m.

Food offering

Sheep hind limb, bundle of sheep ribs and a horse rib.

Other animal remains

Horse and cattle heads (mandibles) and horse foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 45-50-years-old man, presenting bilateral osteoarthritis of the elbows and a fracture of the right fifth metacarpal. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, horse harness (buckle and ring, gilded rivets), iron banding (fragment), knife

Xiongnu prestige items: belt buckle in iron and silver*, iron lamp*

Potteries: 3 vessels

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

An iron lamp was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 27

GPS : 47.7663, 102.44932

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.30 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 2.55 m long, 1.55 m wide, then narrows to 0.90 meters in width at a depth of 2.65 meters, resulting in a volume of 8.7 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method.

Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.85 m long, 0.57 m wide, minimum height: 0.25 m.

Food Offering

Caprine rib and limbs.

Other animal remains

Horse: head (mandible) and foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 25-30-years-old woman, presenting bilateral osteoarthritis of the elbows and a fracture of the right fifth metacarpal. Most of the skeleton is in anatomical connection, except for a few vertebrae and the left humerus. The skull, some vertebrae and ribs, and the left shoulder are missing.

Associated goods

Knife, birch bark (fragment)

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments), bronze bell*

Potteries: 2 vessels, fragments (1)

Wealth index*: 2

Tomb 28

GPS : 47.76751, 102.45029

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 6.55 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 3.05 m long, 2.28 m wide and 3.10 m deep, with an estimated volume of 21.6 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is poorly preserved, making it difficult to determine the components of the walls (plank or squared log), and even more so its method of assembly. Interior dimensions: 2.48 m long, 1.35 m wide, minimum height: 0.25 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. Exterior dimensions: 2.48 m long, 0.75 m wide, minimum height: 0.25 m.

Food offering

Right shoulder and hind limb of a lamb, bundles of ribs from caprines and deer (or possibly a small horse?).

Other animal remains

Horse head (mandible) and foot, cattle hind limb used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 25-30-years-old woman, presenting a dental fracture typical of nut or hazelnut cracking behavior.

Associated goods

Chopstick (1), a hairpin or possibly a pharmaceutical scoop with ram's head (1), horse harness (bit, gilded rivets, hook?), wooden spoon (?), iron banding, bone needle, adornment (glass beads), deer antler

Xiongnu prestige items: gilded rivets, belt* (plate), calligraphy-related items* (stone container, bronze and leather spatula, and wooden disc), iron lamp*

Imported items: lacquerware (2 trays, fragments), pot

Potteries: 4 vessels, including paired pots, fragments (1)

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

An iron lamp was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 107BC - 59AD (95.4% probability, Poz-84436)

Tomb 29

GPS : 47.76758, 102.45024

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 7.22 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 3.40 m long, 1.86 m wide and 2.90 m deep, with an estimated volume of 18.3 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked logs, in the blockbau style,

with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.42 m long, 1.15 m wide, minimum height: 0.12 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 2.13 m long, 0.67 m wide, minimum height: 0.12 m.

Food offering

Shoulders, forelimb (forearm) and hind limb of a ewe, loin (lumbosacral segment) and spare ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse: heads (mandible) and forelimb used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine (ram head).

Individual

The poorly preserved individual is a 25-35-years-old woman. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the right forearm and hand, as well as in the pelvis and lower limbs, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Knives, one of which is in a lacquered sheath; spindle whorls; iron tool (?), a point with a terminal ring; adornment (a bracelet made of glass beads on each wrist).

Xiongnu prestige items: iron cauldron* (leg fragment), iron belt* (with plaque-buckles), silver ring, iron lamp*.

Imported items: lacquerware (oval dish, knife sheath).

Potteries: 5 vessels, including one of two paired pots.

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

An iron lamp was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 30A

GPS : 47.76763, 102.4504

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 2.00 m long, 0.60 m wide and 1.15 m deep, with an estimated volume of 1.4 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

No coffin elements could be identified. Only the bottom of the pit was lined with longitudinal wooden planks.

Food offering

None.

Individual

The individual is a 25-30-year-old man, presenting a fracture of the left 7th rib and a fracture of the distal quarter of the left ulna. The skeletal remains are largely disturbed, except for the forearms and the left fibula, which are preserved in anatomical position.

Associated goods

Iron clasp.

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

No coffin.

Tomb 30B

GPS : 47.76763, 102.45044

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 4.91 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 1.62 m long, 1.28 m wide and 1.56 m deep, with an estimated volume of 3.00 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks joined edge to edge, with the bottom and the cover each formed from a single longitudinal plank. Interior dimensions: 1.00 m long, 0.35 m wide, minimum height: 0.21 m.

Food offering
Sternal plate of a sheep.

Individual
The individual is a 1,5-2,5 years-old boy. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the right forearm, hands and lower limbs, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods
Adornment (one blue glass bead and two cowrie shells).
Imported items: cowrie shells, likely originating from the Indian Ocean or the China Sea.

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 30C

GPS : 47.76766, 102.45043

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (150° north), measures approximately 2.52 m long, 1.49 m wide and 2.55 m deep, with an estimated volume of 9.6 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of thick planks assembled using mortise-and-tenon joints. Notches are present at each end of the longitudinal walls, into which transverse walls are fitted to support the cover. The cover itself is composed of longitudinal planks. A half log, still bearing its bark, is placed atop the lid, roughly at the center of the coffin. The bottom consists of four longitudinal planks, two of which overlap lengthwise: the first measuring 1.10 m and the second 0.90 m. Interior dimensions: 1.80 m long, 0.48 m wide, minimum height: 0.35 m.

Food offering

Ewe's hind limb recovered from a pot and a bundle of sheep and cattle ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse forelimb and pelvis, and sheep foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 20-25 years-old man. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Knife, birch bark box featuring zoomorphic designs (a billy goat and possibly a horse), wooden fastener, adornment (beads made of gilded glass, glass, wood, and stone).

Potteries: 5 vessels

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 47BC-74AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116274)

Tomb 31

GPS : 47.76742, 102.44994

Surface stone circle
Average diameter: 4.35 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (160° north), measures approximately 2.28 m long, 1.00 m wide and 1.93 m deep, with an estimated volume of 4.4 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, 4 to 6 cm thick, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. The cover is held by stone blocks at the walls. Three transverse planks have been identified on these blocks, positioned in the eastern half of the coffin. A large block rests on two of them. Interior dimensions: 1.68 m long, 0.46 m wide, minimum height: 0.27 m.

Food offering

A sheep loin and hind limb were placed from one pot, with a sheep vertebra and rib in a second pot.

Other animal remains

Horse head (mandible) and cattle ribs used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is an elderly woman, with cervical osteoarthritis and inflammatory reactions at the base of the metatarsals.

Associated goods

Knife, spindle whorl, adornment (blue glass bead).

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments)

Potteries: 3 vessels

Wealth index*: 3

T.32

Tomb 33

GPS : 47.76751, 102.45

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 3.04 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 2.55 m long, 1.45 m wide and 1.98 m deep, with an estimated volume of 7.3 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The cover consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.93 m long, 0.55 m wide, minimum height: 0.22 m.

Food offering

Forelimb of a billy goat and caprine ribs found in a pot.

Other animal remains

Horse foot and cattle head used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine (ribs, limbs).

Individual

The individual is an elderly woman presenting cervical vertebral osteoarthritis with posterior synostosis between the 3rd and 4th vertebrae, osteoarthritis of the left hip, and spondylolysis of the 5th lumbar vertebra. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Poteries: 1 vessel, fragments (1)

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 34

GPS : 47.76799, 102.45045

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 13.8 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (140° north), measures approximately 3.50 m long, 2.10 m wide and 4.3 m deep, with an estimated volume of 31.6 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

Only the burial chamber is identifiable, preserved solely as faint woody traces. It is built in the blockbau style, possibly from in-

terlocked logs. The cover consist of transverse planks, with seven recorded in the western half of the chamber. Exterior dimensions: 2.55 m long, 1.85 m wide, minimum height: 0,50 m.

Food offering

A caprine rib.

Other animal remains

Horse (34/2): forelimb (humerus) and hind limb used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual. In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (34/1, shoulder, sacrum, hind limb), Cattle (extremities), Caprine (axis, humerus, and neonatal scapula), Dog/Fox (head).

Individual

The individual is a woman, over 30 years old, found without anatomical connection, presenting osteoarthritis of the cervical vertebrae and of the right knee.

Associated goods

Chopsticks (3), bronze rings (2)
Xiongnu prestige item: iron cauldron* (leg fragment)

Imported items: lacquerware (lug-handled bowl with swan decoration, tray)

Potteries : 4 vessels, including one with a tamga (stamp/seal) on the base

Wealth index*: 2

Tomb 35

GPS : 47.76813, 102.45055

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8.5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3 m long, 1.70 m wide and 2.98 m deep, with an estimated volume of 15.2 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from inter-locked logs, approximately 8 to 10 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style. No element of the bottom or the cover is preserved. Interior dimensions: 2.35 m long, 1.12 m wide, minimum height: 0.35 m. The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of thick planks, 3 to 4 cm thick. Each lateral side is formed by a single plank, while the transverse ends are made of two planks. The structure is joined using mortise-and-tenon joints at the ends of the longitudinal elements. Both the cover and the bottom are composed of longitudinal planks, likely consisting of two planks. The coffin rests on two transverse wooden battens, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. Interior dimensions: 1.80 m long, 0.52 m wide at the east end and 0.32 m at the west end, minimum height: 0,27 m.

Food offering

Sheep ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse : head and foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 16-19 year-old adolescent, without anatomical connection, represented only by the skull, mandible, the first three cervical vertebrae, the distal epiphysis of the left femur, and a few hand bones.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows, horse harness (bit, buckles)

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments)

Potteries: fragments (4), and a ceramic lamp

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp, with charcoals, was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Tomb 36

GPS : 47.76819, 102.45067

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 13 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 3.44 m long, 2.05 m wide and 5 m deep, with an estimated volume of 35.3 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs, approximately 12 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style, with a bottom and a cover made of transverse planks. Interior dimensions: 3 m long, 1.50 m wide, minimum height: 0.50 m.

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom consists of three longitudinal planks, each nearly 20 cm wide. The cover is not preserved. Interior dimensions: 1.95 m long, 0.63 m wide, minimum height: 0.45 m.

Large blocks were found between the chamber and the coffin, on the eastern side, along with disturbed artifacts and bones, suggesting that they were moved by looters. These blocks seem to have been moved aside rather than extracted and may have originally rested on top of the chamber cover or the coffin.

Food offering

Thorax and bundle of horse ribs.

Other animal remains

Horse (34/1) with head and foot, and foal (34/2) with foot used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Caprine (ribs, radius), Marmot (heads).

Individual

The individual is an elderly man, without anatomical connection, presenting vertebral osteoarthritis, particularly in the cervical spine, and osteoarthritis of the left shoulder.

Associated goods

Chopstick (1), knife, bow decorated with an engraved motif of a horseman and arrows, horse harness (bit, bronze decorations and iron bell), possible

scabbard, antler pieces (2), swords (2), buckles and rivets.

Xiongnu prestige item: silver belt* with animal-style and geometric plaques and buckles

Imported items: lacquerware (bowl, dish, fragments)

Potteries: 3 vessels, fragments (2)

Wealth index*: 2

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 112BC - 55AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116275)

Tomb 37

GPS : 47.76834, 102.45053

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5.4 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 2.75 m long, 0.85 m wide and 2.3 m deep, with an estimated volume of 5.4 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin, poorly preserved, is made of planks, with an undetermined joining method. It is slightly trapezoidal. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.90 m long, 0.60 m wide at the east end and 0.50 m at the west end, minimum height: 0.45 m.

Food offering

Sheep ribs placed in a pot.

Individual

The individual is a 40–50-year-old man, without anatomical connection, presenting vertebral osteoarthritis and a fracture of the distal quarter of the left ulna.

Associated goods

Probable bone whistle, adornment (gold earring).
Xiongnu prestige items: gold earring*
Potteries: 4 vessels, and a pot base used as a lamp substitute

Wealth index*: 2

Specific Funerary Practices

A ceramic lamp (base) was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, underneath the intact pots, suggesting intentional concealment.

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 162BC – 46AD
(95.4% probability, Poz-116277)

Tomb 38

GPS : 47.76836, 102.45063

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8.4 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3.10 m long, 1.55 m wide and 4.17 m deep, with an estimated volume of 20 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The chest, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked squared logs, approximately 10 to 12 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. The cover is not preserved. Interior dimensions: 2.47 m long, 1.15 m wide, minimum height: 0.10 m.

The dimensions and construction of the chest correspond more typically to those of a funerary chamber. No elements of a coffin were observed; however, due to the very poor preservation and evidence of looting, it is likely that a coffin once existed.

Food offering

Cattle ribs, sheep head in the northeastern corner of the burial pit.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (scapula), Cattle (ribs, vertebra, hind limb).

Individual

The individual is a 20–30-year-old woman, represented by few remains, without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Possibly a hairpin, with scoop end
Potteries: 4 vessels

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 39

GPS : 47.76838, 102.45083

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 15 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (115° north), measures approximately 4.50 m long, 3.40 m wide and 5.30 m deep, with an estimated volume of 81.1 cubic meters. Large stone blocks are arranged along the walls of the burial pit, beginning at a depth of 3.30 m.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, slightly trapezoidal, is built from interlocked squared logs, in the blockbau style. No element of the bottom or the cover is preserved. Interior dimensions: 2.70 m long, 2 m wide at the east end and 1.80 m at the west end, minimum height: 0.30 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom consists of three longitudinal planks, each nearly 20 cm wide, and the cover consist of longitudinal planks. It rests on two transverse wooden battens, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. The coffin is decorated on its walls and lid with an alternating pattern of iron quadrilobed motifs and crosses, spaced every 25 cm. Based on this spacing, 8 to 9 quadrilobed motifs can be reconstructed per longitudinal plank. Iron bands reinforce the corners of each plank and complete the decorative scheme. Interior dimensions: 2.35 m long, 0.60, minimum height: 0.20 m.

Food offering
Unidentified.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (ribs, forelimb, hind limb), Cattle (tibia), Caprine (vertebrae, rib, hind limb), Dog/Fox (tooth).

Individual

The individual is a 30–40-year-old woman, without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Mirror* (fragments), adornment (stone pendant)
Xiongnu prestige item: cauldron* (leg, fragments), quadrilobed motifs*
Imported items: lacquerware (tray, fragments), mirror
Potteries: 2 vessels, 5 fragments, minimum 7 pots

Wealth index*: 1

Remark

A second mandible was found in the fill of the burial pit; the light dental wear suggests it belonged to a young individual.

Tomb 40

GPS : 47.76853, 102.45106

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 13.6 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 4.60 m long, 3.60 m wide and 5.30 m deep, with an estimated volume of 87.61 cubic meters. Large stone blocks are arranged along the walls of the burial pit.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, approximately 8 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style. The cover consist of transverse planks, three of them are preserved at the east end. Interior dimensions: 2.60 m long, 1.95 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom consist of longitudinal planks, it rests on two transverse wooden battens, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. The coffin is decorated on its walls with iron quadrilobed motifs ; however, the overall decorative scheme could not be identified. Interior dimensions: 2.07 m long, 0.60-0.70 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

Food offering

Tail portion of two sheeps, including lumbar and caudal vertebrae.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function (grave marker, food offering, food waste, symbolic meaning, or other role): Horse (thorax, humerus, femur), Foal (forelimb), Caprine (radius).

Individual

The individual is a 35–45-year-old man, without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Knife, bow, horse harness (buckles, gilded rivets, silver mounts and leaf-shaped ornaments), belt (with gold plaque)
 Xiongnu prestige items: horse harness with silver decorations, gold ornament*, belt* (with gold plaque), gold-covered rivets, iron lamp*, quadrilobed motifs*
 Imported items: lacquerware (bowl, with griffin and seal, tray, fragments)
 Potteries : fragments (2)

Wealth index*: 1

Specific Funerary Practices

An iron lamp was found in the funerary chamber, in a disturbed position.

Tomb 41

GPS : 47.7681, 102.45011

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5.9 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 2.60 m long, 1.60 m wide and 2.20 m deep, with an estimated volume of 9.2 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs, approximately 9 to 10 cm in diameter, in the blockbau style. The cover is partially preserved : between 9 and 11 transverse planks have been identified. These planks measure approximately 1.35 m in length, 0.20 m in width, and 3 to 4 cm in thickness. Interior dimensions: 2.05 m long, 1.10 m wide, minimum height: 0.54 m.

The coffin, which is relatively well preserved, is made of two planks per side, each 3 to 4 cm thick. The planks are joined using mortise-and-tenon joints, both between the individual boards and at the corners of the structure. The cover is partially preserved: one longitudinal plank remains in place along the northern side of the coffin. The bottom is composed of three longitudinal planks, likely mirroring the original construction of the cover. The coffin rests on two transverse wooden battens, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. Internal dimensions: 1.75 m long, 0.60 m wide, minimum height: 0.31 m.

Food offering

Ribs and hind limb of sheep.

Other animal remains

Horse: feet used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a woman, aged over 50 years, presenting osteoarthritis in the vertebrae and knees, a healed fracture of a left rib, and a fracture of the distal quarter of the right ulna. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the right lower limb and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Knife, deer antler, spindle whorl, adornment (blue glass beads), belt (probable belt plate)

Potteries: 4 vessels, and a pot base

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 107BC – 59AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116278)

Tomb 42

GPS : 47.76816, 102.45012

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5.4 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (110° north), measures approximately 2.60 m long, 0.83 m wide and 2.32 m deep, with an estimated volume of 5 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method, with a bottom made of longitudinal planks. Interior dimensions: 1.62 m long, 0.50 m wide, minimum height: 0.35 m.

Food offering

None.

Other animal remains

Horse: Head, forelimb and feet used as a grave marker or as part of a concluding funerary ritual.

Individual

The individual is a 25–30-year-old woman, without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Chopsticks (2), knife blade fragment, deer antler, a flat iron ring, iron rivets (18), adornment (gilded glass bead and probable shell).

Pottery: fragment (1)

Wealth index*: 3

Remark

Fragments of parietal and right maxilla were also recovered from the fill of the burial pit; they may have been introduced during looting.

Tomb 43

GPS : 47.76823, 102.45005

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 6.2 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (125° north), measures approximately 2.80 m long, 1.10 m wide and 2 m deep, with an estimated volume of 6.2 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin, slightly trapezoidal, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. The bottom consists of longitudinal planks, while the cover is composed of transverse planks. Interior dimensions: 2.10 m long, 0.63 m wide at the west end and 0.50 m at the east end, minimum height: 0.35 m.

Food offering

Sheep's right hind limb, with tail portion of other sheep recovered from pot 1 and a bundle of caprine ribs.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (rib, foot), Cattle (mandible, foot).

Individual

The individual is a 30–35-year-old man, with a fracture of the glenoid cavity of the right scapula. The individual is completely disturbed.

Associated goods

Horse harness (bit, iron rings and rivets)
Potteries: 2 vessels

Wealth index*: 3

Remarks

The feet of this individual, still in anatomical connection, were placed on one of the pots located outside the coffin; their displacement occurred while the articulations were still intact.

A second left femur was recovered from the upper levels of the burial pit fill. Its advanced state of degradation is consistent with exposure to open-air conditions, similar to bones that have remained exposed at the surface.

Tomb 44

GPS : 47.76824, 102.45012

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5.5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 2.10 m long, 0.70 m wide and 0.70 m deep, with an estimated volume of 1.2 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

None.

Food offering

Shoulder and hind limbs of a sheep placed in a pot.

Individual

The individual is a 45–50-year-old man, presenting osteoarthritis in the vertebrae, left talus, and left navicular, a fractured rib, a fracture of the left metatarsal, and ankylosis of the phalanges of the first ray of the left foot. The individual is completely disturbed, except tibias and fibulas.

Associated goods

Iron knife blade, and a perforated bone artefact
Potteries: 3 vessels, fragments (2)

Wealth index*: 3

Specific Funerary Practices

No coffin.

Tomb 45

GPS : 47.76826, 102.45019

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (125° north), measures approximately 2.30 m long, 1.25 m wide and 1.40 m deep, with an estimated volume of 4 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks. Each side consists of two overlapping planks, 18 cm high, presumably fitted with mortise-and-tenon joinery. Both the bottom and the cover consists of two longitudinal planks. It rests on two wooden battens, 6 cm de diameter, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. Interior dimensions: 1.80 m long, 0.55 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

A clamping system was used to secure the cover: two pairs of beam holes, spaced 1.35 m apart, were cut into the walls of the burial pit. The northern hole measure 10 cm across and 17 cm deep, while the southern hole measure 17 cm across and 27 cm deep. Remains of transverse beams were found within the beam holes.

Food offering

Shoulder, ribs and hind limb of sheep.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (shoulder, hind limb).

Individual

The individual is a 40-50-year-old man, presenting a distal fracture of the left clavicle. Partial anatomical connections are preserved in the forearms, hands, lower limbs and feet, while the rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Iron belt buckle, iron rings (3), fragment of wooden object, adornment (stone bead), fragments of iron plate
Pottery: 1 vessel

Wealth index*: 3

Dating

Radiocarbon dating: 42BC - 85AD (95.4% probability, Poz-116279)

Tomb 46

GPS : 47.76832, 102.4501

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 5.2 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (105° north), features slight ledges along the north, south, and west walls. It measures without ledges approximately 2.80 m long, 1 m wide and 2.75 m deep, and with ledges approximately 2.60 m long, 0.80 m wide and 2.75 m deep, with an minimal estimated volume of 5.7 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks. Each side consists of two overlapping planks, presumably fitted with mortise-and-tenon joinery. Both the bottom and the cover consists of two longitudinal planks. It rests on two planks, 15 cm wide, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. Interior dimensions: 1.85 m long, 0.56 m wide, minimum height: 0.40 m.

The ledges of the pit support a wooden cover, positioned 20 cm above the coffin. It consists of seven transverse planks, still visible on the western half, between 12 and 15 cm wide, as well as a tree trunk, with visible branch stubs, placed on the western side.

Food offering

Hindquarter of a lamb and ribs deposited in a pot.

Other animal remains

In the pit fill, without a clearly defined function: Horse (foot), Cattle (femur), Caprine (ribs, forelimb, tibia).

Individual

The individual is a man, over 40 years old, presenting an ossified thyroid cartilage, a fracture of the head of the right second metacarpal and a fracture of the distal third of the right tibia. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow and arrows (including a whistling arrow), horse harness (bit, iron buckles), birch bark (dish), axe, probable bone spoon, adornment (glass bead), belt (iron buckle)
 Potteries: 4 vessels

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb 47

GPS : 47.76873, 102.45035

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 13 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (110° north), measures approximately 3.82 m long, 2.51 m wide and 4.40 m deep, with an estimated volume of 42.2 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The burial chamber and the coffin are very poorly preserved, with only weak traces of wood remaining.

The funerary chamber, poorly preserved, is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style. No element of the bottom or the cover is preserved.

Dimensions: 3.46 m long, 2.20 m wide, minimum height: 0.60 m.

The coffin, also poorly preserved, is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Only the longitudinal southern side and bottom are identifiable. The coffin is decorated on its walls with iron quadri-lobed motifs ; however, the overall decorative scheme could not be identified. It rests on two battens, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit.

Tomb 48

GPS : 47.76887, 102.45038

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 16.5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 4.80 m long, 3.50 m wide and 4.67 m deep, with an estimated volume of 78.5 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked squared logs in the blockbau style, covered of transverse planks. Dimensions: 3.20 m long, 2 m wide, minimum height: 0.57 m.

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Both the bottom and the cover consists of longitudinal planks. It is decorated on its walls with iron quadrilobed motifs ; however, the overall decorative scheme could not be identified. The coffin rests on two planks, raising it slightly above the floor of the pit. Dimensions: 2.62 m long, 1 m wide.

Food offering
Unidentified.

Individual

The individual is a 40–45-year-old man, presenting a fractured rib and a fracture of the left clavicle. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Bow, iron ring, iron fragments

Xiongnu prestige items: quadrilobed motifs*

Potteries: fragments, and a pot base used as a lamp with the upper part of an iron lamp

Wealth index*: 2

Specific Funerary Practices

A lamp, composed of a pot base and the upper part of an iron lamp, was discovered outside the chamber, in the northwest corner, suggesting intentional concealment.

Archaeological dataset of tombs excavated before
the french-mongolian field missions

Tomb #6

GPS : 47.76642, 102.44949

Expedition conducted in 2001 by the Mongolian National University (Ulaanbataar, Mongolia)

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 8 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (90° north), measures approximately 4 m long, 1.80 m wide and 3.45 m deep, with an estimated volume of 24.8 cubic meters.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The coffin is made of longitudinal planks, with an undetermined joining method. Interior dimensions: 2.40 m long, 0.81 m wide.

Food offering

Bundle of ribs from caprines.

Individual

The individual is a woman, with some anatomical connections preserved : the left forearm, the pelvis, the lower limbs and the feet. The rest of the skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Spindle whorls (2), bronze fragment, adornment (blue and amber beads)

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments)

Potteries: 2 vessels, fragments

Wealth index*: 3

Tomb #8

GPS : 47.76735, 102.44991

Expedition conducted in 2003 by the Mongolian National University (Ulaanbataar, Mongolia)

Unpublished.

Tomb 97

GPS : 47.76884, 102.4502

Joint expedition conducted in 2005 by the Silkroad Foundation of Saratoga (California, U.S.A.) and the Mongolian National University (Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia)

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 11.5-12 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (120° north), measures approximately 3.70 m long, 2 m wide.

It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

No elements of a burial chamber or coffin have been preserved.

Food offering

Unidentified.

Individual

The individual is an adolescent girl, probably between 16 and 20 years old. Without anatomical connection, the entire skeleton is disarticulated.

Associated goods

Horse harness (bit, iron and bone decorations), wooden toggle

Xiongnu prestige items: iron and bronze cauldron*

Imported items: lacquerware (bowl with a gilt brass rim, with stamp, and fragments of an eared cup and two bowls or cups)

Potteries: 4 vessels and a lamp

Wealth index*: 2

Tomb 100

GPS : 47.76856, 102.45045

Joint expedition conducted in 2005 by the Silkroad Foundation of Saratoga (California, U.S.A.) and the Mongolian National University (Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia)

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 9.5 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, east-west (100° north), measures approximately 2.76 m long, 1.53 m wide. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style. Interior dimensions : 1.95 m long, 0.97 m wide.

The coffin has not been preserved, only the iron quadrilobed motifs were recovered. They likely decorated its sides. The overall decorative scheme could not be identified.

Food offering

Unidentified.

Individual

The individual is a woman, found in anatomical position, except for the head and cervical vertebrae.

Associated goods

Spindle whorl, adornment (carnelian bead), belt (belt plaques), twisted wire

Xiongnu prestige items: bronze cauldron*, quadrilobed motifs*

Imported item: mirror*

Potteries: 5 vessels and a lamp

Wealth index*: 1

Tomb 109

GPS : 47.76752, 102.45046

Joint expedition conducted in 2005 by the Silkroad Foundation of Saratoga (California, U.S.A.) and the Mongolian National University (Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia)

Surface stone circle

Average diameter: 12 m

Grave pit

The grave pit, southeast-northwest (130° north), measures approximately 3 m long, 2 m wide and 3.30 m deep, with an estimated volume of 19.8 cubic meters. It shows signs of looting.

Architecture

The funerary chamber, slightly trapezoidal, is built from interlocked logs in the blockbau style. Interior dimensions : 2.36 m long, 1.36 m wide at the east end and 1.23 m wide at the west end, minimum height: 0.25 m.

No elements of a coffin have been preserved.

Food offering

Unidentified.

Individual

The individual is an adult (not studied), found completely disarticulated, without anatomical connection.

Associated goods

Lacquer-handled knife, horse harness (bit), adornment* (gilded glass beads, gold earring, turquoise), stone container (fragment), iron fragments

Xiongnu prestige items: iron cauldron* (leg fragment), gold earring*, turquoise*

Imported items: lacquerware (fragments), mirror* (fragments)

Potteries: fragments (2) and a lamp

Wealth index*: 1

